

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF COMPLEX THERAPY ON PARAMETERS QUALITY OF LIFE AND DYSFUNCTIONS CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7121142>

Abstract

To study the dysfunctions of cardiorespiratory system and medical aspects of quality life in patients with remodeling the right ventricle of hearts at patients with bronchial asthma. The more severe disadaptation of the disorders of cardiorespiratory system in bronchial asthma. The significant increase in the functional state of the lungs, increase of blood oxygen saturation and increase of physical tolerance in the patients with bronchial asthma who took complex therapy resulted in improved clinical parameters and quality of life. As a result of research Infringements of cardiorespiratory system and QL are negatively correlate PAPav condition and remodeling of the right ventricle of hearts.

Keywords: quality of life, of physical tolerance in the patients, clinical parameters, bronchial asthma, cardiorespiratory system,

The medicosocial importance of the bronchial asthma (BA) problem steadily grows last years. In the USA with asthma suffers 7,2 % of the population or 20 million Americans, in the countries of the European Community prevalence with asthma makes 2-7 %. In England 50 % of patients can be referred to chronic obstructive illnesses of lung and only 9 % - referred to bronchial asthma [4,6]. Formation of cor pulmonale (CP) is the heaviest complication of lung diseases. Cor pulmonale in many respects predetermines the failure of disease, except for sharp reduction in quality of life (QL). It is substantially caused by, that the bronchial asthma concerns to group psychosomatic diseases, as in its origin mental and somatic factors are closely bound, creating complex relationships of cause and effect [5,7,8]. The reason of growth of prevalence and death rate from BA complicated with cor pulmonale in Uzbekistan is the hypodiagnosis and later revealing. To adjust the early diagnosis, adequate preventive maintenance and treatment CP, it is necessary to specify pathogeny of this disease and the factors resulting and aggravating its current [2,3]. At the same time still there is obscure the mechanism of remodeling development right ventricle (RV) of hearts at patients with cor pulmonale.

With this relationship, the complex estimation of the broad audience parameters of the structurally-functional condition of cardio-respiratory system, represents interest. These parameters determine the functional status and medical aspects of quality of life in patients with cor pulmonale [5].

At BA, special interest represents studying changes at the vegetative and microcirculation link

level of blood circulation at various stages of the illness development, and it is important not only for more full disclosing of the pathogenetic mechanisms of this disease, but also for the development of complex adequate treatment [1]. One of the such methods of therapy at patients with BA, complicated with cor pulmonale and probably inhalationtherapy gliserozini.

The purpose of research. Studying the interrelations of the structurally-functional condition of cardiorespiratory system and medical aspects of quality life in patients with remodeling the right ventricle of hearts at patients with bronchial asthma, complicated cor pulmonale.

Materials and methods. 32 patients with BA, complicated with cor pulmonale and 30 healthy persons (HP) were surveyed. At patients were estimated pulmonale hypertension (PH) without dilatation of right ventricle (DRV) - (the level average of pulmonare arterial pressure (PAPav) more than 25 mm.hg.c.) on dopplerechocardiography (DopplerEchoCG) parameters and with DRV (thickness of forward wall of RV is less than 5 mm, at front-back size RV is more than 2,5 sm).

Patients BA, complicated CP with pulmonale hypertension (1st group) and patients BA, complicated CP with dilatation of right ventricle (2nd group) were surveyed.

Depending on methods of treatment patients were divided into the following 2 groups: 1st group (12 patients) and 2nd group (20 patients) received basic therapy (BT) on (GINA, 2006 y.) and inhalationtherapy (IT) with gliserozini.

Besides specific methods of treatment, all patients received the following general medical complex: respiratory gymnastics, hydroaeroionization with iods, medical (expectorating) herbal tea drinks, circular shower, massage of a thorax, a session of psychotherapy.

Researching the patients were carried out at the arrival day and after 10 procedures.

Studying the quality of life parameters of BA patients complicated with cor pulmonale was carried out on specialized Seattle questionnaire and estimated by marking system. Seattle questionnaire allows to estimate the level of a physical, emotional condition, professional suitability and satisfaction treatment at the patients.

1. Parameters of physical condition (FC) were estimated on 18 questions which allow to estimate physical activity and to characterize appearing the decrease degree in a physical condition. 2. Parameters of emotional condition (EC) of the patient were estimated on 5 questions which defined the degree of internal surviving and emotional loading of patients at falling ill. 3. Parameters of QL in professional suitability (PS) were estimated on 4 questions which allowed to estimate reactions of patients to extreme conditions for them, short wind and the complicated breath. 4. Parameters QL of satisfaction were estimated by treatment (ET) on 2 questions, reflecting an estimation of mutual relations of the doctor and the patient from a position of training programs.

According to the recommendations of American echocardiographers society (on Hatle and Angelson, 1985 y.) the following parameters of a diastolic fillings spectrum of diastolic function (DF) RV were calculated with DopplerEchoCG's help: E/A-ratio of early and auricular fillings' speed; TF (m/s) - time of early filling delay; TIR (m/s) - time of isovolumic relaxations and auricular filling's fraction (AFF, %). Analyzed the level of average pulmonare arterial pressure.

Functional condition of ventilating ability pulmonare (VAP) defined on Medikor (Hungary) device, with the estimation of forced exhalation volume for 1 sec (FEV1, %), lung's vital capacity (FVC, %) and index Tiffno (FEV1/FVC, %).

Results are processed with the help Excel software package, using t - criterion Student. Distinctions between investigated parameters were authentically recognized at $p < 0,05$.

Results and discussion. Results of research before treatment at BA patients complicated cor pulmonale with PH and DRV, parameters quality of life and also expressiveness of changes in the specified groups were reduced ambiguously. So BA patients complicated CP with dilatation of right ventricle were worse adapted to all fields of activity. The analysis of results has shown the decrease in points on physical condition scale and software on $1,9 \pm 0,08$ and $3,16 \pm 0,04$ point that was lower in 2,7 and 2,2 times than the greatest possible point (5,2 and 7 points), and emotional condition and estimated by treatment have been reduced to $2,87 \pm 0,05$ and $2,32 \pm 0,06$ points, at the greatest possible estimation in 5,2; 7; 7 and 5,3 points, ($p < 0,05$). Patients of this group had fear of physical activity, to carry out

usual professional duties and a dissatisfaction with treatment.

At bronchial asthma patients complicated CP with pulmonale hypertension parameters of FC, EC, PS and ET have been reduced to $2,96 \pm 0,09$; $2,57 \pm 0,05$; $3,09 \pm 0,05$ and $2,59 \pm 0,04$ points ($p < 0,05$). It is necessary to note, that at bronchial asthma patients complicated PH with DRV the tendency of QL reduction was more expressed on a physical condition and satisfaction by treatment, at BA patients complicated CP with PH on emotional condition and professional suitability in restriction of ability to live ($p < 0,05$) were observed.

Before treatment in parallel with disfunction of ventilating ability pulmonare, was observed the infringements of lung hemodynamics and quality of life patients. So, the increasing of PAPav, volume of the forced exhalation for 1 sec, vital capacity of lung were observed and index Tiffno were reduced in comparison with similar parameters of HP ($p < 0,005$).

In treatment dynamics at BA patients complicated PH parameters of a quality life: FC, EC, PS and ET were the best in comparison by patients CP with DRV, reliability of parameters after treatment ($p < 0,05$).

It was established, that quality of life parameters in therapy dynamics in all groups adaptation to active physical activity was authentically improved and was increased. Also improvement of the psychological condition that is expressed in authentic reduction of depression and disturbing, improvement of the emotional control and memory, satisfaction by life, improvement of social adaptation of patients were established. Comparising the dynamics of QL parameters in 1st group, that increasing of the physical, emotional status parameters and professional suitability appeared a little bit significant, than in 2nd group.

Reduction of TF, TIR, AFF and PAPav, and also increase of E/A ($p < 0,05$, reliability of distinction with parameters before treatment) were defined. The received facts shows, that at the surveyed patients pressure decreasing in lung arteries conducts to the reduction of pressure in RV hearts. At the result there is a reduction of TIR, TF and AFF duration and the gradient decreasing of pressure between the ventricules. From this, positive shifts in RV essentially influence to the activity of heart and remodeling endotelium of cardiovascular system.

Carrying out the correlation analysis between QL, VAP parameters, indexes lung hemodynamics and remodeling of RV hearts it was marked, that with the improvement of FEV1 bronchial passableness, FC, EC, PU and ET parameteres improved ($r = 0,64$ have improved FC, EC; 0,45; 0,26 and 0,21, $p < 0,03$). Decreasing PAPav level resulted to the improvement of FC, EC, PU and ET ($r = -0,74; -0,65; -0,58$ and $-0,27$, $p < 0,01$). The interrelation between the increasing of E/A and FC, EC, PU and ET ($r = -0,57$ is established; $-0,49; -0,38$ and $-0,19$, $p < 0,05$) was established.

The received data testifies that including inhalationotherapy gliserozini into the complex therapy of BA patients complicated cor pulmonale on the background of basic therapy, allows to increase ventilating ability of lung, to lower hemodynamic loading on the right departments of heart, and to improve the structure

of RV hearts diastoles. It is necessary to note, the interconnected infringements of respiratory system and at QL patients remodeling heart's right ventricle improved after the holding procedures, and also weight of illness is reduced and collaterally raises QL of these patients.

Researches showed changing of the quality of life patients sphere before treatment are parallel to infringements of bronchial passableness, pulmonale hemodynamic and DF of right ventricle. Progressing of pulmonale hypertension and development of cor pulmonales at BA patients are closely connected to the development of psychovegetative factors' dysfunction of regulation, and it is necessary to note producing the plan of treatment patients of this category [8]. Mutual burdening and progressing of DF RV infringements and pulmonale hemodynamic are based on a generality of some parts of patogenesis: development of hypoxia, infringements of cardio pulmonale microcirculation and pulmonale hypertension [5]. It was marked collaterally improvement QL and VAP, PAPav levels, and also DF RV conditions at BA patients complicated cor pulmonale, coming after complex treatment with applying inhalationotherapy gliserozini on the background of basic therapy.

Conclusions. At bronchial asthma patients complicated CP with dilatation of right ventricle is more expressed the reduction of quality of life on a physical condition and satisfaction by the treatment, at BA patients complicated CP with pulmonale hypertension on an emotional condition and professional suitability ($p < 0,05$), that is necessary to note during the adequate treatment. Infringements of respiratory system and quality of life are positively correlate ventilating ability pulmonare, average of pulmonare arterial pressure

condition and remodeling of the right ventricle of hearts; inhalationotherapy on the background of basic therapy improve the above stated pathogenetically interconnected infringements ($p < 0,05$).

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